

Polarographic Trace Analysis of Chromium

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Manuscript received 3 April 1987, revised 21 January 1988, accepted 25 March 1988

Chromium(III) has been determined by differential pulse polarography from a 0.05 M sodium salicylate medium with a minimum determination limit of 0.1 ppm. Although chromium(III) is reduced in two steps yielding two distinct peaks at -0.956 and -1.394 V (vs Ag/AgCl (satd. KCl) reference electrode), the latter is well suited for its determination. Simultaneous determination of trace amounts of Bi^{III}, Pb^{II} and Cr^{III} in a mixture is also found possible by this procedure.

BESIDES gas chromatography¹, atomic absorption spectroscopy², and high performance liquid chromatography³, a number of polarographic methods have also been reported for trace determination of chromium⁴⁻⁷. However, most of them deal with determination of chromium(VI). The present communication brings out details of trace determination of chromium(III) by differential pulse polarography (DPP) in salicylate medium. The minimum detection limit is 0.1 ppm of Cr^{III} and relative mean deviation 1.5%. The method is precise and accurate, and enables determination of Bi^{III}, Pb^{II} and Cr^{III} simultaneously.

Experimental

All measurements were performed with a Metrohm-E-506 polarecord instrument. The three-electrode system consisting of DME and Ag/AgCl (satd. KCl) as working electrodes, and Pt wire as auxiliary electrode was used. Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained during recording of polarograms. Standard solution of Cr^{III} was prepared from CrCl₃·6H₂O (AnalaR). Sodium salicylate (Merck, Pa) was used as supporting electrolyte. All other chemicals used were of A.R. or Pa grade, and triple-distilled water was used.

Recording conditions: The following conditions were found to be optimum for recording the differential pulse polarograms: initial potential, -0.2 V; scan range, -0.2 to -1.7 V; scan rate, 4 mV s⁻¹; paper speed, 2 mm s⁻¹; drop rate, 1.0 s⁻¹; pulse amplitude, 4 mV and 40 mV; current sensitivity, 1.0 × 10⁻⁹; total volume, 25 ml; Cr^{III}, 5 ppm and deaeration time, 15 min.

Procedure: An aliquot of 0.5 M sodium salicylate solution (2.5 ml) was transferred to the polarographic cell and to it was added an aliquot of Cr^{III} solution containing 125 μg of the metal. Total volume was made upto 25 ml, deaerated for 15 min and polarogram recorded as described above (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Differential pulse polarogram of Cr^{III} (5 ppm) in 0.05 M sodium salicylate medium.

Results and Discussion

Chromium(III) is known to undergo two-step reduction: Cr^{III} to Cr^{II} and Cr^{II} to Cr⁰, exhibiting two distinct peaks at E_p -0.8 and -1.35 V vs SCE⁸. In the present studies, twenty different electrolytes were tested as supporting electrolytes for Cr^{III}. It was observed that in 0.05 M sodium salicylate medium, the Cr^{III} to Cr^{II} reduction peak was obtained with E_p = -0.956 V, while the second peak corresponding to Cr^{II} to Cr⁰ reduction appeared with E_p = -1.394 V vs Ag/AgCl (satd. KCl). The latter peak is more prominent and distinct than the former, which appears as a rather broad hump. Hence, the Cr^{II} to Cr⁰ reduction peak has been considered as 'analytical peak' in the present determinations. The I_p value obtained for 5 ppm of Cr^{III} at the second reduction signal in 0.05 M sodium salicylate medium is much larger than that obtained in any other medium.

Polarograms of various concentrations of Cr^{III} (0.1 - 10 ppm) were obtained. A linear concentra-

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tion-current relationship was observed over the entire range. Pulse amplitudes of 40 and 4 mV were used for concentration ranges 0.1–1.0 and 1.0–10 ppm, respectively.

The minimum determinable limit observed was 0.1 ppm of Cr^{III}. The relative mean deviation, standard deviation and coefficient of variation values at 0.1 and 5 ppm of Cr^{III} are 1.5 and 0.95; 0.15 and 0.66, and 0.250 and 0.150%, respectively.

Interference of Cu^{II}, Bi^{III}, As^{III}, Zn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mn^{II}, Sn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}, Co^{II}, Mo^{VI} and V^V on determination of 5 ppm of Cr^{III} was studied. Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mo^{VI} and V^V interfere seriously; the others are tolerated to a ratio of 1:100. The procedure is thus fairly tolerant and may be applied to the determination of Cr^{III} in presence of the above non-interfering ions.

Simultaneous determination of Bi^{III}, Pb^{II}, Cr^{III}: The above procedure could be applied to the determination of Bi^{III}, Pb^{II} and Cr^{III} simultaneously in a mixture. Bi and Pb exhibit well-defined peaks (Fig. 2) at -0.064 and -0.356 V, respectively (scan range 0.0 to -1.5 V). Synthetic mixtures containing varying amounts of Bi (2–10 ppm), Pb (2–50 ppm) and Cr (2–10 ppm) were analysed. The percentage recovery from each of the above ions was calculated using both standard addition and calibration curve methods. They are found to be quantitative in each case.

Fig. 2. Simultaneous determination of Bi^{III} (2 ppm), Pb^{II} (5 ppm) and Cr^{III} (5 ppm) in 0.05 M sodium salicylate medium.

Anodic or cathodic stripping voltammetric procedures, which are normally known to provide enhanced sensitivity, are not well suited for chromium determination^{4,9,10}. Catalytic polarography^{11,12} renders the procedure open to the 'matrix effect' which may possibly limit its use in analysing a variety of samples. Differential pulse polarography, on the other hand, provides a simple, efficient, convenient and widely applicable method for trace determination of chromium without any significant loss of sensitivity^{13,15}. The recommended procedure is simple, rapid and has high tolerance towards the presence of other cations.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation, West Germany for donation of the polarographic equipment. One of the authors (A.A.P.) is thankful to the Department of Atomic Energy, Government of India, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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